

were found to tolerate sheath rot (score < 1); M11-57-5-1 (Bhadra), M23-69-1-1-1, and M23-83-1-1 tolerated bacterial blight (score < 1).

M23-17-1-1 and M23-69-1-1 were found to possess tolerance for both sheath blight and sheath rot, diseases that are serious in the area. ■

Varietal response to bacterial blight and stem rot under artificial epiphytotic conditions

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Two experiments tested 56 varieties and lines at the Rice Research Station, Kaul, during May-October 1980. In the first experiment, the yields of 11 promising high yielding varieties and lines were

compared with those of cultivars Jaya and Palman 579. The entries were planted in 15-m² plots in a randomized block design with 3 replications. Two rows of the susceptible check TN1 were planted between two consecutive plots. In the second experiment, 43 varieties and lines were planted in 3-m-long 2-row plots to identify a resistance source for bacterial blight (BB) and stem rot (SR).

BB inoculation was at maximum tillering. The upper 5-cm leaf-tip portions were cut with a sickle dipped in inoculum prepared by soaking pieces of infected leaves in water for 20 minutes. SR inoculation was done in the laboratory on excised internodes (with intact nodes at both ends) collected at flowering stage by the cut-stem wound method.

Observations on intensity of BB and SR were recorded after 14 and 10 days, respectively, in accordance with standard methods. Under BB stress, IET4141, IR36, and Prasad yielded 5.85, 5.59, and 5.54 t/ha or 32% 26%, and 25% more than the check variety Jaya.

IET4141 and Prasad were resistant to SR, IR36 and HAU-6-163 were susceptible. IR36 and Prasad matured 11 days earlier than IET4141. Grain sterility ranged from 5.02 to 12.65 in resistant varieties and 13.54 to 51.89% in susceptible ones (Table 1).

In the second experiment, 16, 22, and 5 entries had resistant, susceptible, and intermediate reactions to SR, and 8, 12, and 14 entries had resistant, susceptible, and intermediate reactions to BB. Damodar and CR206-6176-260 were resistant to both diseases (Table 2). ■

Table 1. Performance of high yielding strains or varieties under high bacterial blight stress at Kaul, India.

Strain or variety	Pedigree	Reaction ^a to		Days to		Grain sterility (%)	Yield ^b (t/ha)
		Bacterial blight	Stem rot	50% flowering	Maturity		
RP633-519-3-8-1-1 (IET4141)	(IR8/BJ 1 43)//IR22	3	1	118	151	12.65	5.85 a
IR36	(IR1561-228)//(IR24/ON)//CR94-13	3	9	105	140	8.14	5.59 a
Prasad	(IR747 B ₂ -6/IR579-48)	3	1	106	140	5.02	5.54 ab
HAU 6-163	Jaya/Palman 246	9	9	106	141	30.63	4.96 abc
CR167-10 (IET4096)	Ratna/Early prolific	5	5	107	142	13.54	4.79 bc
Palman 579	IR8/Tadukan	5	1	105	140	14.86	4.49 c
HAU 1-38-1-1	Jaya/Jhona 349	9	9	105	140	38.19	4.43 cd
Jaya	TNI/T141	9	9	112	146	17.95	4.43 cd
PR 106	IR8/(F'eta S/Bellepatna)	9	1	112	146	15.08	4.30 cde
6473 (IET2729)	-	7	3	110	143	27.18	4.24 cde
6475 (IET2730)	-	5	1	110	143	21.71	4.15 cde
HAU 2-97-1	Jaya/Jhona 351	9	5	94	129	41.99	3.42 de
HAU 1-227-1	Jaya/Jhona 349	9	9	96	131	51.89	3.15 e

^aBased on the Standard Evaluation System for Rice scales. ^bMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Table 2. Reaction of lines or varieties to stem rot and bacterial blight at Kaul, India.

Line or variety	Pedigree or origin	Reaction ^a to	
		Stem rot	Bacterial blight
Basmati 370	Pure line selection	1	7
Jhona 349	Pure line selection	3	9
IR8	(Peta/DGWG)	9	7
Jaya	(TNI/T141)	9	9
Pusa 2-21	(IR8/TKM6)	1	7
Sona	(GEE 24/TN1)	3	7
Improved Sona	-	1	5
Ratna	(TKM6/IR8)	5	7
Zenith	U.S.A.	9	7
Benibhog	-	7	7
Damodar	-	1	3
CO 13	-	9	3
HAU 1-6-1	(Jaya/Jhona 349)	5	7
HAU 1-38-1-1	(Jaya/Jhona 349)	9	9
HAU 3-103-3	(IRB/Jhona 351)	9	5
HAU 5-162-3	(Palman 579/Basmati 370)	9	7

(continued on page 7)

The International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) invites all scientists to contribute concise summaries of significant rice research for publication. Contributions should be limited to one or two pages and no more than two short tables, figures, or photographs. Contributions are subject to editing and abridgement to meet space limitations. Authors will be identified by name, title, and research organization.

Table 2 (continued)

Line or variety	Pedigree or origin	Reaction ^a to	
		Stem rot	Bacterial blight
HAU 6-163-2	(Jaya/Palman 246)	9	9
UPRM 202	(Basmati Mutant)	9	5
UPRM 500	Hansraj Mutant	9	5
PAU 1-608-A	(Basmati 370/IR8-36)	7	5
PAU 41-30-6-2-5	(Phulpattas 72/Mutant 65)	9	9
PAU 128-1191-PR 303	(IR305-3-17-1-3/IR661-1-140-3)	1	5
CRR 89-5-1-1 RPSC 14	(Ratna/Domsiah)	3	5
CRR 89-5-4-1 RPSC-51	(Ratna/Domsiah)	3	5
CRR 89-5-4-2 RPSC-52	(Ratna/Domsiah)	9	7
CR 167-10	(Ratna/Early Prolific)	5	3
CR 206-6176-260	(Vijaya/Domsiah)	1	3
CR 209-6253-262	(Ratna/Domsiah)	5	3
FH 661		9	7
RP 967-4-1-2-4	(Improved Sabarmati/Sona)	9	3
ADT 32	(IR20/Pusa 33)	9	5
ADT 14166	(Pusa 140/Pusa 33)	3	9
ADT 14185	(Pusa 140/Ratna)	5	5
TRB 63	Basmati Mutant	9	5
SST ₁ - 1898	Punjab	9	7
SST ₁ - 1906	Punjab	3	7
SFC III	(IR8/NP 49)	9	1
R 575	Himachal Pradesh	1	7
O 12990-2/6-10-2	(IR8/Pankli 203)	1	7
IR4422-480-2	(IR2049-134-2/IR2061-125-31)	1	5
IR8073-231-3-3	(IR4-11/IR2035-290-2-3)/IR2153-26-3	3	5
IR9752-303-3-1-3	(IR28/Kwang-Chang-Ai)/IR36	9	3
Nong Nghiep 75-5	(IRS/D 268)	9	5

^aBased on the Standard Evaluation System for Rice Scales.

Pathogenic variability in *Xanthomonas oryzae*

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Thirty-six rice varieties were artificially infected in the field with 24 isolates of *Xanthomonas oryzae* (Uyeda et Ishiyama) Dowson in September 1973 and April 1974. The objective was to select suitable parents for determining genes for resistance and probable differentials for research on pathogenic specialization.

Twenty-six of the varieties were selected on the basis of their known reactions to 1 or 2 virulent isolates of *X. oryzae*; 16 were morphological markers of the 12 linkage groups in rice, included to identify characters associated with resistance.

The rices were artificially infected by the clipper method developed by Kauff-

man, using 2-day-old cultures suspended in sterile distilled water. The optical density was adjusted to 1.5 with Spectronic-20 at 620 nm. The spread of infection was measured (in centimeters) below the point of infection 15 days later.

The infection generally spread more in September than in April, with some notable exceptions. The response to seasonal factors in variety-isolate interactions was differential (see table).

Differential varieties should have short growth duration (120-130 days or less) and be insensitive to photoperiod. Short-duration varieties facilitate the multiplication and maintenance of pure seeds, the raising of seedlings to the flag-leaf stage for artificial infection, and other operations. Differential varieties should also show clear-cut resistant and susceptible reactions (the spread of infection in susceptible reaction should exceed 10 cm).

BJ1, Wase Aikoku 3, AC3550, and AC616 were completely resistant to 9 isolates, and, therefore, poor candidates as differentials, but good resistance

Differential reaction between isolate and rice varieties between September and April inoculations in Madras.

Variety	Isolates showing differential reaction
AC616	C
JBS376	C H201
AC806	C
AC5169	H J
Pirurutong	J H110 H146
Sigadis	H14 H1110 H66 H100
AC1063	D
ARC 142	H24
AC5607	H167 H200
T1242	H167 H100
MNP153	H167
SLO 16	H200
AC467	H200
Vijaya	H200 H201
JBS376	H34
M18	H201 H34
Early Prolific	H201
AC1224	H201
Lacrosse/Zenith-Nira	H110 H146 G
MNP153	H100
MNP152	G

donors. One or two of this group, however, could be included in the differential set to detect new virulent races in a region.

PTB 10, Cauvery, IR8, and TN1, being susceptible to all isolates, are also poor differential candidates. TN1 might be included as a test variety in infection studies.

The following appear to be good candidates as differentials: AC616, AC5169, AC3551, AC1063, ARC11249, ARC142, AC5607, JBS376, Bluebelle, and Lacrosse/Zenith Nira. Only Sigadis had consistently low infection against all isolates in kharif and is, therefore, a good donor for resistance to Indian isolates.

The variability of the pathogen and its response to environmental fluctuation suggest the need for a rigid standardization of infection procedures. ■

Relation between leaf blast and neck blast disease on paddy in trials during 1980 kharif in India

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This study sought to understand the relationship between leaf blast and neck